

DOES BOARD INDEPENDENCE MODERATE THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ENVIRONMENTAL DISCLOSURE AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF 30 MOST CAPITALISED FIRMS IN NIGERIA?

MURTALA MOHAMMED SANI^{1*}, LUCKY OTSOGE ONMONYA² and
UDEOZOR, PAUL EJIKE³

¹Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nile University of Nigeria.

²Phd, Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Nile University of Nigeria.

³Institute of Development Finance and Project Management.

*Corresponding Author Email: ibnamsani@yahoo.com

Abstract

This study assessed how the moderating role of independent directors affects the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance of the listed 30 most capitalized companies on the floor of the Nigerian exchange group. This study covers 10 years (2014-2023). Due to the nature of the research, an ex-post factor design was used. Data were collected from the annual reports of the 25 most capitalized firms listed on the Nigerian exchange group. Panel data analysis was used, and the major findings are that environmental disclosure has a significant negative effect on market capitalization. Board independence has an insignificant negative effect on market capitalization, but the Moderating effect of board independence has a significant positive effect on the market capitalization of listed performing companies in Nigeria. Suggesting that an increase in independent board members increases firm value. Of listed performing companies in Nigeria. It is recommended that the management of public interest companies effectively communicate and create more awareness among existing shareholders and potential investors on the importance of environmental disclosure. The study will encourage robust interest in patronizing shares of companies that engage in greener production.

Keywords: Environmental Disclosure, Board Independence, Financial Performance, Agency Theory.

1. INTRODUCTION

Corporate environmental disclosure is one of the important voluntary disclosures done by listed companies in recent times. The emphasis on this issue is a result of increasing global concerns about reducing environmental deterioration caused by alarming pollution due to increasing waste, which results in climate change and global warming. The adverse impact of industrial production has become a threat to the physical environment. It has created health hazards that are detrimental to host communities, customers, employees, and society at large. Climate change caused mainly by greenhouse gas emissions has made some companies address environmental issues. It is making companies more concerned with the environment and also profit. Hence, there is a need to publish more information about the environment (Sang et al., 2023). Yahaya et al. (2023) pointed out that in recent times, companies have improved corporate communication with stakeholders by providing information on measures taken to protect the environment through environmental disclosures. Environmental disclosure, as a significant element of voluntary disclosure by organizations, is an integral part of corporate social responsibility (Abubakar et al., 2023; Abgineh et al., 2023).

Companies, especially those whose operations are environmentally sensitive, are expected to disclose the adverse effects of their activities on the environment. Yahaya et al. (2022) pointed out that in recent times, companies have improved corporate communication with stakeholders by providing information on measures taken to protect the environment through environmental disclosures. The disclosure of environmental information in annual reports is becoming an important aspect of corporate external reporting.

In recent times, there have been many studies on environmental disclosure and performance. For instance, Haixia Wu and Jianping Li (2023) did a study on the relationship between environmental disclosure and the financial performance of heavy-polluting enterprises in China. Studies such as Abgineh, Ghanbary, and Rahmani (2023) examine the influence of environmental disclosure (ED) on financial performance. In Nigeria, Kurawa and Shuaibu (2022), Ogunode and Adegbe (2022), Abubakar, Sadiq, and Abdullahi (2023), Abgineh, Ghanbary, and Rahmani (2023) examine the influence of environmental disclosure on the financial performance of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria.

As public demand for a clean and safe environment increases and core corporate stakeholders such as investors and communities become more aware and interested in environmental issues, it is expected that they will be attracted to companies with more disclosure and more investment, patronage, and a guaranteed tranquillity in operation may likely increase resulting to financial performance in terms of profitability and market value. The scenario may not be the case in Nigeria, as there is considerable doubt about the increase in environmental disclosure. Potential investors may not see that environmental disclosure can improve the profitability and market value of companies.

A core aspect of disclosure in annual reports and financial statements is the availability and operation of a robust corporate governance structure with regard to board independence. The board, depending on the composition of executive and non-executive independent directors, may propel environment disclosure in response to public expectations and patronage, a quest to please stakeholders such as host communities and civil society organizations for stable business operation and government for creating an enabling environment. The board may make concrete decisions on improving corporate environmental performance and disclosing such information if this will improve the operating environment and financial performance. Haniffa and Cooke (2002) argued that corporate governance can affect a company's disclosures since board members determine the extent of disclosures in the company.

Environmental disclosure is a contemporary accounting and financial reporting issue that is actively being researched. There are quite a number of studies on environmental disclosure, but most are in Western and Asian countries, as shown in the empirical review. Findings on studies on the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance are mixed and inclusive (Arumona, 2021; Abgineh et al., 2023). Therefore, an introduction of a moderating variable may provide a novel direction and a more robust finding.

The extent to which board independence can contribute towards enhancing environmental disclosure as a panacea for financial performance in an era of increasing advocacy and agitation

for companies to be environmentally responsible is not known. In Nigeria, no study on environmental disclosure has used board attributes such as board independence as a moderating variable. To the best of the researcher's knowledge, studies on environmental disclosure using an entire sector in Nigeria have not been extended to 2022. No study has been done on environmental disclosure using the 30 most capitalized companies.

This study will fill the gap by using a moderating variable - board independence to assess their effect on the relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance. Thus, this study will provide empirical evidence on the link between environmental disclosure and financial performance as well the moderating role of board independence of the 30 most capitalized companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Limited (NXG) in Nigeria for a period of 10 years - 2014 to 2023.

The study's objectives are to assess the effect of Environmental Disclosure on market capitalization and investigate the moderating effect of board independents.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Conceptual Review

The main issues in this study include environmental disclosure, board independence, financial performance, and the link between the concepts.

2.1.1 Environmental Disclosure

Environmental disclosure is the presentation of information on how an organization deals with the mitigation of environmental challenges caused by its activities as a contribution to a clean and safe environment. Abubakar et al. (2023) Environmental disclosure is a significant element voluntarily disclosed by organizations as an integral part of corporate social responsibility. In recent times, companies have improved corporate communication with stakeholders by providing information on measures taken to protect the environment through environmental disclosures (Yahaya et al., 2023). Many companies are now involved in greener production in order to mitigate adverse environmental impacts (Murashima, 2022).

Gatimbu and Wabwire (2016). (2016) said that corporate environmental disclosure entails reporting on the impact of company activities on the natural environment, such as waste management, recycling, carbon management, emission, pollution, wetland, and wildlife conservation.

Companies, especially those whose operations affect the environment, are expected to disclose their financial commitments to mitigating the adverse effects of environmental hazards (Solomon, 2020). Wahyuningrum et al. (2020) said that a company discloses its environmental disclosure by providing its annual report and sustainability report as a responsibility to society and the environment. Abubakar (2023) pointed out that environmental disclosure is a significant element voluntarily disclosed by organizations as an integral part of corporate social responsibility.

Reporting on the information concerning the corporate environment arises as a company effort to meet the needs of stakeholders and also as a part of management effort to obtain legitimacy from stakeholders. Environmental disclosure will indirectly require the company to maintain and manage the environment responsibly, so environmental information is essential for the company to be disclosed. Moreover, Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) investing is increasingly popular among investors,

Conventional accounting systems are limiting since they fail to address sustainability concerns directly. They have failed to address economic growth against social and environmental needs in order to balance the different needs of various stakeholders. Sustainability has become a major pillar of today's business activities. Yahaya et al. (2022) pointed out that in recent times, companies have improved corporate communication with stakeholders by providing information on measures taken to protect the environment through environmental disclosures. Istiqomah et al. (2020) stated that Environmental disclosure is the disclosure or reporting of information relating to the management and performance of the corporate environment that is disclosed on the corporate reports or company websites.

Nguyen, et al. (2023). Said that Environmental Accounting Information Disclosure is the most recent novelty in corporate non-financial information reporting practice. Yahaya, et al. (2022). In recent times, companies have improved corporate communication with stakeholders by providing information on measures taken to protect the environment through environmental disclosures. Ifada et al. (2023), who examined the company's environmental responsibility in responding to current environmental issues, pointed out that regulations from stakeholders and the increasing public awareness of pollution are new challenges for companies.

Financial Performance

Environmental Disclosure will likely improve financial performance in terms of profitability and share price. Profitability measures include return on assets, return on equity, earnings per share, and operating profit margin, while share value measures include the market price of the share and market capitalization.

Market capitalization is used in this study as a measure of financial performance. Market capitalization, or "market cap," is the total market value of a publicly traded company's outstanding common shares owned by stockholders (Graham et al., 2010). Since it represents the "market" value of a company, it is computed based on the current market price (CMP) of its shares and the total number of outstanding shares. Outstanding shares refer to the number of stocks that a company has issued. The formula for the market cap is:

$$\text{Market Cap} = \text{Price Per Share} \times \text{Shares Outstanding}$$

Market cap is also used to compare and categorize the size of companies among investors and analysts. It is also used to rank the relative size of stock exchanges, which is a measure of the sum of the market capitalizations of all companies listed on each stock exchange.

Lubatkin and Shrieves (1986) argue that market-based performance measures incorporate all relevant information and are, therefore, not limited to a single aspect of firm performance, unlike accounting measures. Some researchers even take the shareholder perspective explicitly and propose that shareholder wealth maximization is the ultimate criterion for achieving the firm's economic objectives (e.g., Johnson et al., 1985).

Tomislava et al. (2021) that market-based measures have better informational value than accounting-based measures. They argued that market-based measures provide better information on the predictability of default risk. However, they acknowledged that the accounting measures have a higher potential to predict distress, like in the case of Enron. They also highlighted that accounting measures are better for private companies that do not have market information.

Ibrahim and Darkal (2018) established that market-based measures are equally exposed to manipulation to the desired market perspective in recent years as many shareholders are more interested in market-based measures. Their findings revealed that market-based accounting measures performance. Alajlani (2019) corroborated the finding that accounting measures of performance measures have a significant positive relationship with market-based measures.

Board Independence

Board independence is an essential part of board characteristics. The board of directors, which is positioned above the chief executive and other managers in the company's hierarchy, plays a strategic role in the firm's decision-making (Ndalun et al., 2021). As a result, team composition and qualities are crucial for effective group decision-making and company performance (Fakile & Adigbole, 2019). Outside directors with a substantial stake in the company's ownership are more likely to exercise their authority to protect their interests as shareholders and those of other shareholders, thereby contributing to a higher level of performance (Bhaghat et al., 1998).

Board independence refers to the state in which all or a majority of the members of a board of directors do not have a relationship with the company except as directors. Fuzi et al. (2016) that explain the board of directors is a collective body that should act in the best interest of shareholders. The board requires a combination of executive and non-executive directors to pursue the shareholders' interests. The non-executive directors on the board will not be able to exercise their duties effectively unless they are independent of management and ensure they provide unbiased business judgment. Independent directors are the people entrusted by shareholders to represent them and will help to reduce agency problems. According to Clifford and Evan (1997), an independent non-executive director is defined as an independent director who has no affiliation with the firm except for their directorship. There is an apparent presumption that boards with significant outside directors will make different and better decisions than boards dominated by insiders.

Furthermore, Fama and Jensen (1983) concluded that non-executive directors play an important role in the effective resolution of a firm's agency problems. Therefore, their presence can lead to straightened and more effective decision-making in the firm. According to Abidin et al. (2016), outside directors generally are viewed as professional referees who unbiasedly

protect the shareholders' interests, helping to prevent or detect any management opportunistic behavior.

CFA Institute (2024) pointed out that to be effective, boards must take steps, both in their structures and in their nominating procedures, to ensure that insiders and executive owners are unable to exercise undue control over the board's activities and decisions. CFA Institute advised that companies with a majority of independent directors are likely to consider the best interests of shareholders first, foster independent decision-making, and mitigate conflicts of interest that may arise. Independent directors are not connected to a company's management other than participating and performing the responsibilities as members of the company's board of directors. These directors have no material pecuniary links or transactions with the company, its promoters, or its management. Independent directors relate to the extent to which a firm's board of directors has autonomy, free from conflicts of interest, which enables them to be accountable and act in the best interests of shareholders. The ratio or percentage of independent directors on the board size is used as a measure for independent directors (Nassirzadeh et al., 2023; Zalata et al., 2022).

Thus, according to Khatib et al. (2020), the presence of independent directors on the board is a signal to the market that the firm is being adequately controlled and seen as creditworthy to attract investors to provide more leverage. Given its relevance, independent directors create greater monitoring of management decisions, reduce agency conflicts among shareholders, and promote the interests of shareholders, as well as the firm's ability to protect itself against uncertainties when there is a higher proportion of independent directors, as argued by agency theory (Fama & Jensen, 1983; Zaid et al., 2020) Thus, the numerous arguments on the appropriate size of independent directors should be vis-à-vis the total board size.

On the other hand, while agency theory suggests that a higher proportion of independent directors can benefit a firm, the resource-dependency perspective (Salancik & Pfeffer, 1978) argues that independent directors can bring valuable advice and diverse viewpoints. However, a board dominated by them may have potential downsides for firm performance, as noted by Scarfarto et al. (2020). According to the findings from the study conducted by Khatib et al. (2021), there is a positive link between board independence and leverage. This finding aligns with the resource dependence perspective proposed by Salancick and Pfeiffer (1978), which suggests that external directors enhance a firm's capacity to navigate the external environment, mitigate uncertainty, and access resources that contribute to fundraising efforts and enhance the firm's reputation. Zaid et al. (2020) pointed out that lenders perceive boards with a high level of independent members as having a strong incentive to meet required expectations and also checks against unnecessary executive actions.

Board independence is determined by the percentage of non-executive directors on the board. A large percentage of non-executives is a strong sign of corporate governance that will encourage transparency and disclosure levels (Habbash, 2015). Hence, it is expected that the presence of a high proportion of independent directors can result in positive firm value. Abdel-Wanis and Rashed (2023) also highlighted the significance of board independence by stating that when a firm has a higher level of board independence, it signals to the market that it is

being closely monitored and operates more efficiently and effectively. Consequently, this positive perception by lenders enhances the firm's creditworthiness and facilitates access to the financing necessary for its business operations. The degree to which board members are dependent on the present CEO or organization is referred to as board independence. Outside directors, as opposed to insiders, who are managers or employees of the firm, or dependent non-executive directors, who have personal and/or professional relationships with the firm other than board membership, maybe a major factor influencing market capitalization.

2.1.4 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework on relationship between Environmental Disclosure and Financial Performance: the moderating role of Board Independence.

Source: Researcher's Conceptualisation, 2024

2.3 Theoretical Review

There are many theories on corporate environmental disclosure. Among these are the stakeholders theory, legitimacy theory, and agency theory. The agency theory is the most suitable for this study because it includes an independent director as a moderating variable.

2.3.1 The stakeholder theory

The stakeholder theory posits that a company's stakeholders can compel the company to disclose social and environmental information because it is their right to know the social and environmental impact of the company's operations. The theory predicts that the relative power of a particular stakeholder group (with power often being defined in terms of the group's control over scarce resources) will determine whether that group receives the accounting information it desires (Deegan, 2005). Clarkson (1995) argues that marking CSR as a business objective is best undertaken by changing intangible social and environmental issues into tangible stakeholder interests.

In recent times, there has been increasing awareness among stakeholders such as investors, customers, supplier groups, communities, and civil society groups on environmental performance issues. Host communities and environmentalists have made powerful stakeholders such as shareholders and debenture holders concerned with environmental management issues in Nigeria. Employees are mainly interested in occupational health and environmental safety issues, and this can make companies provide environmental information in these areas.

2.3.2 Legitimacy theory

Legitimacy theory posits that for a company to continue to exist, it must act in congruence with society's values, norms, and beliefs. Deegan (2005) points out that Legitimacy theory predicts that in certain circumstances, companies will use positive or favorable disclosures in an effort to restore their legitimacy. Dowling and Pfeffer (1975) were the proponents of organization legitimacy theory. They contended that since organizations are part of a larger society, they will continue to ensure that they operate within the values, norms, bounds, and beliefs of the society so that their activities can be recognized by society as 'legitimate.' Nihal (2015) explains that environmental disclosures can be used to repair legitimacy insofar as such disclosures address society's concerns supposedly offset criticism, and cultivate societal support.

Branco and Rodrigues (2007) explain that apart from providing economic benefits, such as profits, wages, and employment, compliance with the law is considered legitimate. It has become necessary for companies to act and be seen acting within the bounds of what is considered acceptable according to the values and norms of society. The company should consider the rights of the public at large and not merely those of investors (Joshi et al., 2011). How a company operates and reports are largely influenced by the social values of the community in which they exist. One way for companies to remain legitimate to the important public is voluntary disclosure of social and environmental information in annual reports. Abgineh et al. (2023) pointed out that companies disclose environmental information to achieve social goals. Companies' financial performance is an important factor in information disclosure; thus, companies should disclose environmental information to maintain their reputation in society.

2.3.3 Agency Theory

Jensen and Meckling's (1976) agency theory provides a framework linking disclosure behaviour to corporate governance. The principal-agent link of the agency theory was improved by Fama (1980) and Fama and Jensen (1983); this deals with the separation of ownership from control, that is, the shareholders and the board of directors, which creates conflict of interest and information asymmetry. Kanakriyah and Raed (2021) explain the concept of agency theory by stating that the diversity of the BOD increases the independence of the board, thus increasing the role of the board in monitoring and tackling agency problems.

Agency theory addresses the challenge of the relationship between the agent and the principal. A core aspect is the reduction of information asymmetry through appropriate financial reporting and minimizing abusive activities of management through adequate

structure and internal control system to provide direction on how the firm should be managed. Gardi et al. (2023) contended that corporate governance increases information transparency and the quality of non-financial information, thereby reducing agency problems between managers and shareholders. Siew et al. (2016) reveal that voluntary disclosing non-financial (social and environmental) information decreases information asymmetry.

Byrd and Hickman, 1992 used the agency theory to justify that independent directors ensure that a company monitoring and control system is efficient in order to reduce agency costs that usually result from conflict of interest, breach of confidentiality, diversion of corporate opportunity, and disclosure of corporate information. Thus, the independent director protects the interests of potential and existing shareholders because of their minimum conflict of interest. They might encourage green investment and, thus, disclosure as a means for improving financial performance.

Yusof and Alhaji (2012) asserted that self-interest syndrome is the bane of the agency problem. The interest of shareholders is to maximize return and not necessarily grow company size except where the growth in size translates into higher earnings for them. The director will also do whatever it takes to improve performance if there is a perceived benefit that accrues to them. Thus, if environmental disclosure improves the profitability or market value of a company, the director will do everything to disclose more information to improve as this will appeal to shareholders and potential investors. Therefore, agency theory provides a strong base for board independence as a moderator between environmental disclosure and financial performance.

Review of Empirical Studies

Environmental Disclosure and Financial Performance

Empirical studies have been conducted on environmental accounting disclosure and the financial performance of companies in many countries. Teoh et al. (1998) and Hossain et al. (2006) revealed that a positive link between environmental disclosure and financial performance exists. However, the evidence for the impact of environmental disclosure on subsequent financial performance was not strong. Norhasimah et al. (2016) show there is a significant relationship between total environmental disclosure and profit margin. However, the findings for three other variables, which are ROA, ROE, and EPS, showed no significant relationship with total environmental disclosures. Karambu et al. (2016) reveal that environmental disclosure has a positive significant effect on the mean financial performance. Murray et al. (2006) show that no relationship was found between corporate social and environmental disclosure and share return. Al-Khadash (2002) reveals no association between social and environmental disclosure and financial performance.

Reveals a positive association between corporate attributes (such as profitability, size and industry type) and the level of disclosure.

Qiu et al. (2016) examined the link between a firm's environmental and social disclosures and its profitability and market value. Findings show that firms with higher social disclosures have

higher market values. Further analysis reveals that higher expected growth rates in the cash flows of such companies drive this link.

Murashima (2022) Long-term investor responses to environmentally friendly news in the food sector are more unfavourable than in the automobile industry. This study did not consider the effect of disclosure on financial performance. Obiora et al. (2022) assessed the impact of environmental accounting disclosure on the profitability of quoted firms in Nigeria from 2017 to 2021. The study concludes that environmental accounting disclosure has a significant impact on financial performance.

Khandelwal and Chaturvedi (2021) examine the outcome of environmental accounting on financial performance amongst the top 100 companies of Indian origin as per their market cap in the year financial year 2018-19. No noteworthy relationship was found between environmental disclosure, Profit Margin and EPS; however, environmental disclosures have a significant effect on ROA and ROE. Pawar and Munuswamy (2024) indicate a significant negative influence of environmental reporting on the ROA and ROE of banks. On the other hand, environmental reporting does not significantly influence the EPS of banking institutions.

Emmanuel and Ifeanyichukwu (2021) revealed that environmental accounting disclosures had a significant effect on Share Price, Return on Asset and Return on equity of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Haixia Wu et al. (2023) show that there is a positive relationship between both mandatory environmental disclosure and voluntary environmental disclosure and financial performance; Alkhuzaie et al. (2023) found that environmental disclosures positively impact the value relevance of industrial firms listed on the Amman Stock Exchange.

However, some studies suggest that environmental disclosure is not favourable to financial performance. Refunds et al. (2018) reveal that environmental disclosures do not affect the firm's market value and do not mediate the effect of financial performance and environmental performance on firm value. Mikial et al. (2019) show that environmental performance has a positive but not significant effect on financial performance, while environmental information disclosure has a negative and significant effect on financial performance.

Kurawa and Shuaibu (2022) revealed a significant positive relationship between EPED, WDCD, PMCD, and EPS while a negative relationship with the TQ of listed Nigerian non-financial companies. This development will help accountants be trained in environmental accounting and reporting.

Ogunode and Adegbe (2022) found that while environmental disclosures (EDD) exhibited a negative effect on Returns on Assets (ROA) and Market Price per Share (MPS) of the sampled firms, Abgineh et al. (2023) financial performance can be directly affected by disclosure of the environmental content Abubakar and Sadiq (2023) This showed that environmental disclosure has positive impact on financial performance of listed cement manufacturing companies in Nigeria. Findings are mixed and inconclusive; based on this empirical and theoretical insight, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H₀₁: environmental disclosure has no significant effect on financial performance

Board Independence and Environmental Disclosure

Maurya (2015) reveals that board independence is not a significant determinant of financial performance. Agyemang et al. (2020), board independence measured by independent directors and the separation of the chief executive officer from the board chairman revealed a positive and significant relationship with EADI. Yahaya et al. (2023) state that board independence has an insignificant inverse influence on the environmental disclosure of the sampled companies. Raimo et al. (2022) show a non-significant impact of board independence.

Ahmed (2023) indicates that board size, board independence and risk management committee independence have a positive effect on IR practices. Ndalul et al. (2021) investigated the relationship between board characteristics and environmental disclosure of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria: The moderating role of firm size with its specific objectives, such as to determine the relationship between board independence and environmental disclosure. The research design adopted was ex-post facto design, while the population and the sample size for the study are the 12 quoted oil and gas companies in the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). The findings of the study reveal that board independence has a negative relationship with environmental disclosure, and firm size significantly moderates the relationship between board characteristics and environmental disclosure.

Trireksani et al.'s (2016) findings show that these companies made moderate environmental disclosure and that there is a significant positive relationship between the size of the board of directors and the extent of environmental disclosure.

Naseer and Rashid (2018) used stakeholder and agency theory to investigate the relationship between CG characteristics and environmental monitoring (ER), which is a component of corporate social responsibility in Pakistan. The findings revealed that environmental monitoring is correlated with greater board size, a higher proportion of elected non-executive members on the board, the separation of the dual position of chairman and CEO, and institutional ownership. Mbonu and Okoye (2023) revealed that Board Independence has a significant and positive effect on Effluent Disclosure. of listed Oil and Gas firms in Nigeria and South Africa.

Sang et al. (2023) suggest that board independence is positively related to reducing GHG emissions. In addition, our evidence shows that firms with higher levels of GHG emissions have better financial performance, but board independence weakens the relationship.

In Nigeria, where there are weak environmental regulations and corporate stakeholders' powers to enforce environmental disclosure. Based on this empirical and theoretical insight, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H₀₃: Board independence has no significant effect on Firm Value of listed companies.

Moderating Role of Board Independence

Ehada et al. (2023) investigated the moderating role of female board membership on the nexus between environmental disclosures and the profitability of non-financial services firms in Nigeria. This study concluded that there is no moderating effect of female board membership on the relationship between female board membership and employee relations, female board membership and local community disclosure, and return on assets of non-financial services firms in Nigeria.

Arumona (2021) found that Environmental Disclosure had a positive and statistically significant effect on the Financial Performance of quoted oil and gas companies in Nigeria during the period under review.

Ogunsola et al. (2024) revealed that environmental sustainability disclosure, particularly when moderated by board independence, significantly influenced the firm value of Nigerian-listed non-financial companies. In contrast, governance sustainability disclosure had a significant impact on the firm value on its own.

Abgineh et al. (2023) revealed that some variables, such as those related to corporate governance, type of industry and macroeconomic variables (economic growth), can affect the relationship between financial performance and disclosure of environmental content. Companies should disclose environmental information to maintain their reputation in society.

Lestaria et al. (2022) show that the board of commissioners and ROE affect firm value, while the audit committee does not. Family ownership strengthens the relationship between ROE and audit committee on firm value but cannot moderate the relationship between independent commissioners and firm value.

The use of board independence as a moderator may not be strong enough to influence environmental disclosure and financial performance. Therefore, the following hypotheses are proposed:

H₀₃: Board independence has no significant effect on the relationship between environmental disclosure and Firm Value of listed companies.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study is a longitudinal study because it involves repeated observation of the same subjects or variables over 10 years (2014-2023). Due to the nature of the research, an ex-post factor design was used. Ex-post facto design is a non-experimental research technique in which pre-existing groups or subjects are compared to ascertain if there are significant differences between variables based on events that occurred in the past. This non-experimental research is similar to an experiment because it compares two or more groups of individuals with similar backgrounds who were exposed to different conditions as a result of their natural histories (Lammers & Badia, 2005). Thus, it is also referred to as quasi-experimental design.

3.2 Population and sample of the study

The population of this study is a total of 30 of the most capitalised companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NXG). However, the purposive sampling method will be used to select 25 companies that are in existence and with required data for the relevant years will be selected for the study (Refer to Appendix 1). They were selected based on the following criteria: 1. being currently active on the NXG; 2. listed on the main board of the NXG before 2013 and have 10-year published annual reports (2014 to 2023) submitted to the NXG; 3. The annual reports should also have information on the study variables.

3.3 Sources and Methods of Data Collection

The main source of data for this study was the corporate annual reports obtained from the Nigeria Exchange Group (NXG). The kinds of data needed for this study were environmental information disclosed in narrative or monetary forms; the various proxies for corporate board characteristics such as board size, board independence and board gender diversity; financial performance data such as revenue, equity, assets, profit after tax, as well as firm age. All parts of the annual reports (the Chairman's Report, Directors' Report, Sustainability Report, Auditors' Report, Financial Statements and Note to Accounts) will be scrutinised for data.

The data collection procedure will involve training three research assistants to identify and obtain data from the annual reports and score CEDI with adequate supervision from the researcher. The research assistants must have postgraduate qualifications in accounting, finance, and management-related disciplines. They will be trained on environmental disclosure themes and indicators in the CEDI checklist and how to identify them in the annual reports of selected companies.

The procedure for collecting data on environmental disclosure involved four steps. First, the annual reports from each sampled company will be scrutinised to check for pages that contain environmental information based on the corporate environmental disclosure index checklist (refer to Appendix 2 for seven (7) environmental themes and 40 environmental indicators used in this study). Second, if environmental information is disclosed, the types of disclosure in terms of the environmental pillars and area of location in the annual report (for example, Chairman's Report, Directors' Report, Financial Statements and Notes to Accounts) will be identified. Third, a dichotomous coding scheme is used to award a score of [1] if an environmental item is disclosed while a non-disclosure item will be assigned [0]. Thus, a company can score a maximum of 40 (100%) and a minimum of 0 (0%).

A Corporate Environmental Disclosure Index (CEDI) checklist with unweighted scores is the research instrument used to collect data on environmental disclosures in annual reports of targeted firms over the timeframe of the study. The CEDI checklist contains seven environmental pillars and forty environmental indicators (refer to Appendix A2). CEDI was developed from prior studies in developed countries. The environmental Themes/indicators were obtained from the CEDI checklist used by Clarkson et al. (2007), who pointed out that

the environmental pillars/indicators in the CEDI were developed by environmental disclosure experts based on the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI). It was used in the work of Clarkson et al. (2008); Clarkson et al. (2011) and Despina et al. (2011).

3.4 Model Specification

$$MCAP_{it} = a + b_1ED_{it} + b_2BI_{it} + b_3BI*ED_{it} + e_{it}$$

Where **MCAP** is the dependent variable,

ED Environmental Disclosure is the independent variable.

BI (Board Independence) is moderating variables.

a is constant or intercept, **b₁ to b₃** are the coefficients of the independent or explanatory variables and **e** is the error term. **i** and **t** are indices for individuals (companies) and time (10 years: 2014-2022) respectively.

3.5 Measurement of Variables

The measurement for the dependents and independent variables is given in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: Variables Description and Measurement

S/N	Independent Variables	Proxy	Acronym	Measurement	Source
1.	Environmental Disclosure	-	ED	Measured by CEDI checklist using a dichotomous approach to score environmental item. With one (1) if disclosed and zero (0) if not disclosed. A percentage of disclosed items over total items is then computed.	Bunaimin, 2010; Islam and Deegan, 2006; Uwuigbe & Olayinka, 2011; Uwuigbe & Jimoh, 2012
S/No	Dependent Variables		Acronym	Measurement	Source
	Financial Performance	Firm Value	MCAP	Total issued Share Capital X Market Price of Share	Butt, et al (2023)
S/No	Moderating Variable	Proxy	Acronym	Measurement	Source
	Board Independence	Board Independence	BI	Proportion of independent Directors	Ifada, et al. (2023),

3.6 Method of Data Analysis

3.6.1 Test of Significance

Panel regression was used in this study; thus, various panel regression options were run. These include Pool Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression and Generalised Least Square (GLS) regression technique, which comprises the Random Effect Fixed Effect regression techniques.

Other robustness tests are the variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test (to test for colinearity), the Hausman specification test (to choose between random effect and fixed effect), the Breusch – Pagan / Cook – Weisberg test (heteroscedasticity) and the Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test (Select between pool effect and fixed effect).

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test was used to test for multicollinearity. VIF measures the amount of multicollinearity in a set of multiple regression variables. The presence of multicollinearity within the set of independent variables can cause problems in understanding the significance of individual independent variables in the regression model. Using variance inflation factors helps to identify multicollinearity issues so that the model can be adjusted. A VIF 10 and above indicates a multicollinearity problem.

To test for heteroskedasticity, the Breusch – Pagan / Cook – Weisberg test is used. The VIF test may show an absence of multicollinearity, but the Breusch-Pagan test for heteroskedasticity may reveal the presence of heteroscedasticity. The benchmark for the Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test is that if the test statistic has a probability of chi value below 5% ($p < 0.05$), the null hypothesis of homoskedasticity is rejected, and heteroskedasticity is assumed. If the data has a heteroskedasticity problem, there is a need for further analysis using the two techniques in panel data analysis: the fixed effect regression and the random effect GLS regression.

A Hausman test was run to decide between fixed or random effects. If the probability of the chi value is significant at 0.05, select the fixed effect option, or select the random effect option if the probability is insignificant at 0.05 (Oscar, 2011). If random effect results are chosen in favour of fixed effects, the R-square overall is interpreted, but if a fixed effect is chosen in place of random, the R-square within is interpreted.

The Breusch-Pagan Lagrange multiplier (LM) test is also used to test for random effects. The LM test helps in deciding between a random effects regression and a pooled OLS regression (Green, 2008). When the probability value of the chi-square is less than 0.05, there is a panel effect, that is, there is a significant difference across entities. If the probability value of the chi-square is more than 0.05, this indicates no evidence of significant differences across entities; therefore, pooled OLS regression is used.

When the mean of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is much higher than the threshold of 10, this indicates that the explanatory variables included in the model were correlated, indicating the presence of multicollinearity between the variables. A more robust regression model the linear regression, correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs) is used (Ghasemi & Zahediasl, 2012).

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics results for the Environmental Disclosure Score (EDS), Board Independence (BI), and Market Capitalization (MCAP).

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max	Obs.
MCAP	4.27	7.65	0.79	54.51	250
EDS	0.53	1.26	0.03	20.00	250
BI	0.19	0.16	0.00	0.58	250
BIEDS	0.10	0.21	0.00	3.08	250

Source: Stata 13 output (2024)

The table above describes the features/characteristics of the study’s variables in terms of market capitalization (MCAP), environmental disclosures (EDS), board independence (BI), and regulating board independence/disclosures. The average scores for the respective variables are 4.27, 0.53, 0.19 and 0.10. The study revealed that market capitalization has the highest maximum, which is 54.51. In contrast, Board Independent has the lowest maximum, which reached 0.58, while the highest minimum, which reached 0.79, is depicted by market capitalization. Finally, the standard deviation results indicate that Board Independent and Moderating Board Independence/Disclosures have 0.16 and 0.21, implying that the variability of their values was low, as indicated by the low standard deviation. Meanwhile, Market Capitalization (MCAP) and Environment Disclosure (EDS), with standard deviations of 7.65 and 1.26, have moderate standard deviations.

4.2.2: Correlation Matrix

The correlation matrix is used to determine the degree of association between the dependent variable and the independent as well as the moderating variables. It is used to detect the problem of multicollinearity. Table 4.3 presents the result of Correlation of multicollinearity between Market Capitalisation (MCAP) and other variables.

Table 4.3: Correlation Matrix showing the association between MCAP and other Variables

Var.	MCAP	EDS	BI	BIEDS
MCAP	1.000			
EDS	0.0117	1.000		
BI	0.2403	-0.169	1.000	
BIEDS	0.1228	0.9399	0.2683	1.000

Source: Stata 13 output (2024)

Table 4.3 is a correlation matrix that explains the association between the dependent and independent variables. This table clearly depicts a positive correlation/association between the EDS, BI, BIEDS, and MCAP, given by coefficients of 0.0117, 0.2403, and 0.1228, respectively. Although there was a positive relationship between the dependent and independent variables of the study, EDS had a negative correlation with BI and a positive correlation with BIEDS. BI had a positive relationship with BIEDS at the 5% level of significance.

Diagnostics Tests

To avoid spurious regression analysis, the regression result was subjected to multicollinearity (to see if the independent variables were suffering from multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity tests).

VIF (Multicollinearity) Test

Table 4.5: Multicollinearity Test (MCAP, EDS and other Variables)

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
EDS	27.97	0.035757
BI	25.99	0.038482
BIEDS	3.26	0.307032
Mean VIF	19.07	

Source: Stata 13 Output (2024)

The residual of the regression analysis was subjected to a multicollinearity test to detect the presence of collinearity among the variables. The result shows that the mean of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) was 19.07, which is much higher than the threshold of 10. The VIF for individual variables was also low for BIEDS, while that of EDS and BI was high. This indicates that the explanatory variables included in the model were correlated, indicating the presence of multicollinearity between the variables. However, linear regression and correlated panels corrected standard errors (PCSEs), the results of which show no autocorrelation problem, indicating the absence of multicollinearity between the variables.

4.2.4: Regression Results

The multiple regression, which captures the environmental disclosures and market capitalisation: moderating role corporate board independence in Nigeria, was analysed using linear regression, correlated panels corrected errors (PCSEs). This was used because the VIF test indicates the presence of multicollinearity between the variables.

The regression results are as follows:

Table 4.8: Regression result using PCSEs (Market Value)

Variables	Coefficients	Std. Err	t-stat	P-value
Constant	4.341673	0.6425654	6.76	0.000
EDS	-6.865509	2.264262	-3.03	0.002
BI	-5.178754	4.495906	-1.15	0.249
BIEDS	44.99423	15.11201	2.96	0.003
R ²				0.1110
F-Stat.				37.98
P-sig.				0.0000

Source: Stata 13 output (2024)

The result of the analysis in Table 4.8 shows that the P-values for (EDS) environmental disclosure (0.00) are significant at a 5% level. This suggests a negative significant effect on the financial performance of listed performing companies in Nigeria. (BI) board independence (0.249) is insignificant at a 5% significant level, suggesting a negative insignificant effect on the financial performance of listed performing companies in Nigeria. The P-value of (BIEDS) moderating environmental disclosure/board independence (0.003) suggests a positive significant effect on the financial performance of listed performing companies in Nigeria. The coefficient of determination (R²) explains that 11% of the variations in the financial performance of listed performing companies in Nigeria can be explained by environmental disclosure and board characteristics (EDS, BI, BIEDS). If the purpose of the R-square is to predict, there is a need for a very large R-square, but if it is just to explain some effect on the dependent variable, 4 % may be appropriate (Karen, 2013). The F statistics test was used to show the model's fitness. The findings indicate that the F statistic is statistically significant at 5%. Thus, it can be inferred that the model is fit to explain the environmental disclosure and financial performance with the moderating role of corporate board independence in Nigeria.

4.3: Test of Hypotheses

The panel regression results in Table 4 show that environmental disclosure has a significant negative effect on the market capitalization of listed performing companies in Nigeria. Based on this outcome, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternate hypothesis states that environmental disclosure has a significant negative effect on market capitalization in Nigeria at a 5% significant level (P = 0.002). The findings infer that a unit increase in environmental disclosure will inversely increase the market capitalization by 6.865509 of listed performing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Board Independence has no significant effect on market value of the listed performing companies in Nigeria.

The regression result in Table 4.8 shows that board independence has an insignificant negative effect on the financial performance of listed companies in Nigeria. Based on this outcome, the alternate hypothesis is rejected, and the null hypothesis states that Board independence has a significant and negative effect on market capitalization in Nigeria at a 5% significant level (P = 0.249). The findings infer that a unit increase in board independence reduces the market capitalization by 5.178754 of listed performing companies in Nigeria.

H₀₃: BIEDS has no significant effect on market capitalization of the listed performing companies in Nigeria.

The panel regression results in Table 4.8 show that moderating environmental disclosure/board independence (BIEDS) has a significant positive effect on the market capitalization of listed performing companies in Nigeria. Based on this outcome, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternate hypothesis states that BIEDS has a significant positive effect on market capitalization in Nigeria at a 5% significant level (P = 0.003). The findings infer that a unit increase in BIEDS will increase the market capitalization by 15.11201 of listed performing companies in Nigeria.

4.5 Discussion

The findings from the linear regression analysis are highlighted below in consonance with the objectives of this study. The following deduction can be made:

The first model of objective one on environmental disclosure and market capitalization was significant and negative. The conclusion of the finding infers that an increase in EDS results from inversely increasing financial performance measured by MCAP. This implies that the MCAP of listed performing companies in Nigeria increases inversely as EDS increases. This finding supports the stakeholder theory, which states that stakeholders have the power to compel companies to mitigate environmental damage caused by their operations. This ensures that companies across industries or sub-sectors will engage in mitigating environmental damage that will be beneficial to respective stakeholders. This usually led to the disclosure of environmental information in annual reports so as to gain stakeholders' support or further investment. Stakeholders' powers include influences exerted by various stakeholder groups on companies. Findings from previous studies show that powerful stakeholders can influence companies to disclose environmental performance information (Cormier & Magnan, 2003; Deegan & Rankin, 1997). The finding supports the assertion that environmental disclosure has the potential to influence its financial performance significantly. Wahyuningrum et al. (2020) said that a company disclosed its environmental disclosure by providing its annual report and sustainability report as a responsibility to society and the environment. Abubakar and Sadiq (2023) pointed out that environmental disclosure is a significant element voluntarily disclosed by organizations as an integral part of corporate social responsibility.

Yahaya et al. (2022) pointed out that in recent times, companies have improved corporate communication with stakeholders by providing information on measures taken to protect the environment through environmental disclosures.

This finding aligns with the results of Abubakar and Sadiq (2023), Abgineh et al. (2023), Yahaya et al. (2022), and Uniamikogbo and Ifeanyichukwu (2021), who found that environmental disclosure has a significant effect on financial performance. On the contrary, Murashima (2022) and Agyemang et al. (2020) establish that there is no relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance.

The first model of objective two, onboard independence and market capitalization, was insignificant and negative. The finding concludes that an increase in EDS results from decreasing financial performance measured by MCAP. This implies that the MCAP of listed-performing companies in Nigeria increases as BI decreases.

The findings justified that independent directors are those who are not connected to the firm or its management in any way other than participating and performing the responsibilities as members of the company's board of directors. This finding was supported by Yahaya et al. (2023), Sang et al. (2023), and Odoemelam and Okafor (2018), who revealed a negative effect of board independence on financial performance. In contrast, Ogunsola et al (2024) and Mbonu and Okoye (2023) indicated that board independence has a significant relationship with financial performance.

5. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary

the major findings are:

- i. Environmental disclosure has a significant negative effect on market value of listed performing companies in Nigeria.
- ii. Board independence has an insignificant effect on financial performance of listed performing companies in Nigeria.
- iii. Moderating environmental disclosure/board independence (BIEDS) has a significant positive effect on market capitalization of listed performing companies

5.2 Conclusion

The conclusion is based on the findings of the study. The findings imply that an increase in environmental disclosure will negatively affect the market value and earnings per share of the most capitalized firms listed on the NGX. The findings infer that a unit increase in board independence reduces the market capitalization by 5.178754 of listed performing companies in Nigeria. An increase in board independence increases the earnings per share, and when it serves as a moderator, it increases the market capitalization of listed performing companies in Nigeria; however, this will reduce the earnings per share.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. Management of public interest companies effectively communicates and creates more awareness among existing shareholders and potential investors on the importance of environmental disclosure. This will encourage robust interest in patronising shares of companies that engage in greener production.
- ii. The board should appoint independent directors with knowledge and passion for environmental issues. These directors can sensitise other executive directors and management to provide environmental reports that positively impact firm value.
- iii. The Security and Exchange Commission (SEC) should ensure that the corporate governance code is complied with to enhance the clear role of the independent director in encouraging environmental disclosure.

5.4 Limitations of the Study

There are a number of inherent limitations in this study.

- i. The sample of this study was taken from the 30 most capitalised listed firms on the NGX. Therefore, the result will have little external validity beyond these companies. The study did not also consider other listed firms, which is a fundamental limiting factor. The result might have been different if they had been included in the study.
- ii. The list of environmental themes or indicators used for computing the level of disclosure and environmental disclosure index might not be exhaustive since other guidelines were

used in addition to the GRI. This can affect internal validity. The result may be different if the number of environmental indicators is increased or another set of environmental indicators is examined.

5.5 Contribution to Knowledge

This study has contributed to extending the frontier of knowledge as it provides empirical evidence of voluntary environmental disclosure by 30 most capitalised in the NGX for 10 years (2014 to 2022) using Board independence as a moderating variable. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this is the first study that deals with Environmental Disclosure and financial performance with the moderating role of board independence using the 30 most capitalised companies in Nigeria. The findings of this study are of practical importance to investors and other regulatory authorities as they should be cautious while interpreting the increases in disclosures related to environmental activities. This study provides empirical evidence that independent directors can provide the impetus for environmental disclosure, which may lead to financial performance as a result of key corporate stakeholders' increasing interest in greener production, such as investors, suppliers, customers, government, and communities.

This study contributes to the literature by showing that board independence moderates the effects of Environmental Disclosure and financial performance. The evidence supports the emphasis of the code of corporate governance that more non-independent directors should be on the boards. This study offers insights to policymakers interested in enhancing the monitoring role of corporate boards.

References

- 1) Abdel-Wanis, N., & Rashed, T. (2023). The significance of board independence on firm monitoring and operational efficiency.
- 2) Abgineh, M., Ghanbary, M., & Rahmani, M. (2023). Financial Performance with emphasis on the role of environmental information disclosure. *Journal of Advances in Environmental Health Research*, 11(1), 53-59.
- 3) Abidin, S., Ishaya, I. V., & M-nor, M. N. (2016). The association between corporate governance and auditor switching decision. *International Journal of Economics and Financial Issues*, 6(7), 77-80.
- 4) Abubakar, R. B., & Sadiq, R. A. (2023). Impact of environmental disclosure on financial performance of cement manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences* 24 (2a), 382-388
- 5) Agyemang, A. O., Yusheng, K., Ayamba, E. C., Twum, A. K., Chengpeng, Z., & Shaibu, A. (2020). Impact of board characteristics on environmental disclosures for listed mining companies in China. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 27, 21188-21201.
- 6) Ahmed, M. M. A. (2023). The relationship between corporate governance mechanisms and integrated reporting practices and their impact on sustainable development goals: evidence from South Africa. *Meditari Accountancy Research*, 31(6), 1919-1965.
- 7) Al-Khadash, H. A. (2002). The association between social and environmental disclosure and financial performance.

- 8) Alkhuzaie, A. S. H., Altarawneh, M., Hikal, H., & Irshoud, J. (2023). Mediating role of competitiveness between corporate governance and performance of Jordanian SMEs. *International Journal of Accounting Research*, 8(2), 47-51.
- 9) Arumona, J., Lambe, I; Ogunmakinde, I (2021). Effect of environmental disclosure on financial performance of quoted oil and gas companies in Nigeria,: [Http://Loc BHU Digital Repository. URI: Http://localhost:8080/Xmloi/Handle/123456789/519](http://loc.bhu.edu.ng/digital-repository/handle/123456789/519)
- 10) Bhagat, S., Carey, D. C., & Elson, C. M. (1998). Director ownership, corporate performance, and management turnover. *Bus. Law.*, 54, 885.
- 11) Branco, M. C., & Rodrigues, L. L. (2007). Issues in corporate social and environmental reporting research: An overview. *Issues in social and Environmental Accounting*, 1(1), 72-90.
- 12) Bunaimin, A. (2010). Environmental disclosure in corporate annual reports: A study of Malaysian public listed companies. *International Business Research Journal*, 3(5), 10–20.
- 13) Butt, H., Noreen, M., & Aslam, H. (2023). Impact of corporate governance on firm performance: Evidence from emerging markets. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 15(2), 200–218.
- 14) Byrd, J. W., & Hickman, K. A. (1992). Do outside directors monitor managers?: Evidence from tender offer bids. *Journal of financial economics*, 32(2), 195-221.
- 15) CFA Institute (2020, October 1). Board Independence & Independent Board of Directors, CFA Institute Research and Policy Centre. <https://rpc.cfainstitute.org/en/policy/positions/board-independence>.
- 16) Clarkson, J., Therivel, R., & Chadwick, A (2007). *Introduction to environmental impact assessment*, Oxford, England: Routledge.
- 17) Clarkson, M. E. (1995). A stakeholder framework for analyzing and evaluating corporate social performance. *Academy of Management Review*, 20(1), 92–117.
- 18) Clarkson, P.M., Overell, M.B., & Charpple, L. (2011). Environmental reporting and its relation to corporate environmental performance. *Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business Studies*, 47(1), 27-60
- 19) Clarkson, P.M., Yue, L.R., Richardson, G.D., & Vasvari, F.D. (2008). Revisiting the relationship between environmental performance and environmental disclosure: An Empirical Analysis. *Accounting, Organisation and Society*, 33(4-8), 303-327.
- 20) Clifford, P., & Evans, R. (1997). Non-executive directors: a question of independence. *Corporate Governance: An International Review*, 5(4), 224-231.
- 21) Cormier, D., & Gordon, I. M. (2003). An examination of social and environmental reporting strategies. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 14(5), 587-617.
- 22) Deegan, C. (2005). *Financial accounting theories*. North Ryde, Australia: McGraw Hill.
- 23) Deegan, C., & Rankin, M. (1997). The materiality of environmental information to users of annual reports. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 10(4), 562-583.
- 24) Deegan, C., & Jeffrey, U. (2006). *Financial Accounting Theories*, Berkshire: McGraw-Hill
- 25) Despina, G. G., Efthymios, E.F., & Antonios, S. (2011, May). The relationship between firm size and environmental disclosure. *International Conference on Applied Economics*, 179-186.
- 26) Dowling, J., & Pfeffer, J. (1975). Organizational legitimacy: Social values and organizational behavior. *Pacific sociological review*, 18(1), 122-136.

- 27) Ehada, S., Okpanachi, J., Agbi, E. S., & Joshua, S. (2023). Environmental disclosures and profitability of non-financial services firms in Nigeria: Moderating role of female board membership. *UMYU Journal of Accounting and Finance Research*, 5(1), 50-63.
- 28) Emmanuel, U., & Ifeanyichukwu, A. P. (2021). Environmental accounting disclosure and financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and International Business Management*, 9(2), 71-81.
- 29) Fakile, G., & Adigbole, E. A. (2019). Effect of board characteristics on financial performance of quoted information communication and technology companies in Nigeria. *Entrepreneurial Journal of Management Sciences*, 6(1), 75-85.
- 30) Fama, E. F. (1980). Agency problems and the theory of the firm. *Journal of Political Economy*, 88, 288-307. <https://doi.org/10.1086/260866>
- 31) Fama, E.F. and Jensen, M.C. (1983) Separation of ownership and control. *Journal of Law and Economics*, 26, 301- 325. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/467037>
- 32) Fuzi, S., Habidin, N., & Zamzulaila, Z. (2016). The importance of independent directors in corporate boards.
- 33) Gardi, B, Aga, M & Abdullah, N. (2023). Corporate governance and financial reporting quality: the mediation role of IFRS, *Journal of Sustainability*, 15(13) 1-19, DO 10.3390/su15139869
- 34) Gatimbu, K. K., & Wabwire, J. M. (2016). Effect of Corporate Environmental Disclosure on Financial Performance of Firms Listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange, Kenya. *International Journal of Sustainability Management and Information Technologies*. 2(2) 1-6. doi: 10.11648/j.ijsmi.20160201.11
- 35) Ghasemi, A., & Zahediasl, S. (2012). Normality tests for statistical analysis: a guide for non-statisticians. *International journal of endocrinology and metabolism*, 10(2), 486.
- 36) Green, W. H. (2008). *Econometrics analysis*, 6th edition Upper Saddle River, New Jersey, Prentice Hall
- 37) Habbash, M. (2015). Corporate governance, ownership, company structure and environmental disclosure: Evidence from Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Governance and Regulation*, 4(4-4), 460-470. https://doi.org/10.22495/jgr_v4_i4_c4_p3
- 38) Haniffa, R. M., & Cooke, T. E. (2005). The impact of culture and governance on corporate social reporting. *Journal of accounting and public policy*, 24(5), 391-430.
- 39) Hossain, M., Islam, K., & Andrew, J. (2006). Corporate social and environmental disclosure developing countries: evidence from Bangladesh. *Proceedings of the Asian Pacific Conference on International Accounting issues*, Hawaii. Retrieved April 19, 2022 from http://www.pub.iges.or.jp/modules/envirolib/upload/96/attach/BE2_3003.pdf
- 40) Ifada, L. M., Najihah, N., Amilahaq, F., & Khatamy, A. A. (2023, February). Conceptual paper of environmental disclosure and financial performance: the role of environmental performance. In *International Conference on Emerging Internetworking, Data & Web Technologies (203-214)*. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- 41) Islam, M. A., & Deegan, C. (2006). Media pressures and corporate disclosure of social responsibility performance information: A study of two global clothing and sports retail companies. *Accounting and Business Research*, 36(4), 41–52.
- 42) Istiqomah, I & Indah, F. S. W. (2020) Factors affecting environmental disclosure in companies listed on the Tokyo stock exchange, *Accounting Analysis Journal*, 9(1) (2020) 22-29
- 43) Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs, and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305–360.

- 44) Joshi, P.C., Suwaidan, M.S., & Kumar.R. (2011). Determinants of environmental disclosure by Indian industrial listed companies in the website: An empirical study. *Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 3(2), 109-130.
- 45) Kanakriyah, R. A., & Raed, M. A. (2021). Board diversity and its effect on agency problems in corporate governance.
- 46) Karen G. M. (2013). *Can a regression model with a small r-squared be useful?* The analysis factor. Retrieved from http://blog.uwgb.edu/banrevg/files/2013/11/Can-a-Regression-Model-with-a-Small-R-squared-Be-Useful_.pdf
- 47) Khandelwal, Ad & Chaturvedi, A. (2021). *Environmental Accounting Disclosures and Financial Performance in India*, Recent Advances in Fields of Accounting, Finance and Management, 2021 Weser Books, Germany 978-3-96492-255-7, S <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3842705> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3842705>
- 48) Khatib, S. F., Feriha Abdullah, D., Hendrawaty, E., & Suleiman Yahaya, I. (2020). Corporate governance mechanisms and capital structure. *International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology*, 29(10S), 993-1003.
- 49) Khatib, S. F., & Nour, A. (2021). The impact of corporate governance on firm performance during the COVID-19 pandemic: Evidence from Malaysia. *Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 8(2), 0943-0952.
- 50) Kurawa, J. M., & Shuaibu, K. (2022). Environmental disclosure and financial performance of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance Research*, 10(2), 31-52.
- 51) Lammers, W. J., & Badia, P. (2005). *Fundamentals of behavioral research*. Belmont, CA: Thomson Wadsworth.
- 52) Lestari, D., Hariyani, E., & Oktari, V. (2022). What do we know about corporate governance, family ownership, and firm value?. *JIFA (Journal of Islamic Finance and Accounting)*, 5(2), 109-120.
- 53) Lubatkin, M. H., & Shrieves, R. E. (1986). Towards reconciliation of market performance measures to strategic management research. *Academic of Management*, 1(3), 497-512.
- 54) Maurya, S. (2015). The role of board independence in determining firm financial performance: Evidence from developing markets. *International Journal of Finance and Corporate Studies*, 7(4), 45–59.
- 55) Mbonu, C. M., & Okoye, E. I. (2023). board characteristics and environmental disclosure of listed oil and gas firms in Nigeria and South Africa. *Journal of Global Accounting*, 9(2), 20 –35 <https://journals.unizik.edu.ng/joga/article/view/2188>
- 56) Mikial, G., Azadi, A., & Hoseini, S. (2019). The relationship between environmental performance, environmental disclosure, and financial performance: Evidence from developing economies. *Journal of Environmental Management and Sustainability*, 8(2), 124–138. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2019.02.014>
- 57) Murashima, M. (2022). Do investors’ reactions to environmentally friendly news announcements differ across industries? A comparative analysis of Japan’s food and automotive industries. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 23(6), 1315– 1333. <https://doi.org/10.3846/jbem.2022.18244>
- 58) Murray, A., Sinclair, D., Power, D., & Gray, R. (2006). Do financial markets care about social and environmental disclosure? Further evidence and exploration from the UK. *Accounting, Auditing & Accountability Journal*, 19(2), 228-255.

- 59) Naseer, M., & Rashid, K. (2018). The relationship between environmental reporting and corporate governance: empirical evidence from Pakistan. In *Globalization*. IntechOpen.
- 60) Nassirzadeh, F., Askarany, D., & Arefi-Asl, S. (2023). The relationship between changes in corporate governance characteristics and intellectual capital. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 16 (133),1-20, DOI:10.3390/jrfm16020133
- 61) Ndalu, T. C., Ibanichuka, E. A. L., & Ofurum, C. O. (2021). Board characteristics and environmental disclosure of quoted oil and gas firms in Nigeria: The moderating role of firm size. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 9(4), 51-62.
- 62) Nguyen, T. A., Le, P. H., Nguyen, H. D., Luong, T. C. T., & Ngo, M. T. (2023). The effect of environmental accounting information disclosure on financial performance of Vietnamese listed industrial firms: The moderating role of Leverage and Big4. *CTU Journal of Innovation and Sustainable Development*, 15(2), 126-138.
- 63) Nihal, J. (2015). The use of environmental disclosures to restore legitimacy in business.
- 64) Norhasimah, N., Mohd, Z. M. Y., & Faizal, F. (2016). Environmental disclosure and its relationship with financial performance indicators.
- 65) Obiora, F., Onuora, J. K., & Sandra, E. C. (2022). An Assessment of the impact of environmental accounting disclosure on profitability of firm in Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Finance and Economics Research*, 10(1), 92-103.
- 66) Odoemelam, N. & Okafor, R.G. (2018). The influence of corporate governance on environmental disclosure of listed Non -Financial firms in Nigeria. *Indonesian Journal of Sustainability Accounting and Management*, 2(1), 25-49.
- 67) Ogunode, O. A., & Adegbie, F. F. (2022). Environmental disclosure practices and sustainable performance of quoted manufacturing companies in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 22(23), 455-469.
- 68) Ogunsola E. A., Daniel, E. K, Orbunde, B, (2024) Moderating role of board independence on the effect of environmental and governance sustainability disclosure on firm value of listed non-financial firms in Nigeria, *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 8(4), 2700-2718
- 69) Oscar, T. R. (2011). Panel data analysis: fixed and random effect (using STATA 10.4). Princeton University. Retrieved from www.dss.princeton.edu/training/.
- 70) Pawar, D. S., & Munuswamy, J. (2024). Does environmental reporting of banks affect their financial performance? Evidence from India. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 42(4), 745-767.
- 71) Qiu, Y., Shaukat, A., & Tharyan, R. (2016). Environmental and Social Disclosures: Link with Corporate Financial Performance. *The British Accounting Review*, 48(1), 102-116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bar.2014.10.007>
- 72) Raimo, N., Nicolò, G., Tartaglia Polcini, P., & Vitolla, F. (2022). Corporate governance and risk disclosure: evidence from integrated reporting adopters. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 22(7), 1462-1490.
- 73) Refunds, R., Adewale, A., & Oladipo, T. (2018). The mediating role of environmental disclosure in the relationship between financial performance and firm value. *African Journal of Accounting, Auditing and Finance*, 10(3), 245–263.
- 74) Salancik, G. R. (1978). *The external control of organizations: A resource dependence perspective*. New York: Harper & Row.

- 75) Sang Joon Kim, Hohyun Kim and Erdal Atukeren (2023). Effects of Board Independence on Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Financial Consequences: Evidence from South Korea, *Environments*, 10(3), 56; <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments10030056>
- 76) Siew, R. Y., Balatbat, M. C., & Carmichael, D. G. (2016). The impact of ESG disclosures and institutional ownership on market information asymmetry. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Accounting & Economics*, 23(4), 432-448.
- 77) Teoh, H. Y., Pin, F. W., Joo, T.T., & Ling, Y.Y. (1998). Environmental disclosures –financial performance link: further evidence from industrialising economy perspective. Nanyang Technology University, Singapore. Retrieved from <http://www.citeseerx.ist.psu.edu>. *The European Accounting Review*, 9(1), 31 – 52.
- 78) Trireksani, Terri & Djajadikerta, Hadrian Geri (2016) Corporate Governance and Environmental Disclosure in the Indonesian Mining Industry, *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 10(1), 18-25 . <http://ro.uow.edu.au/aabfj/vol10/iss1/3>
- 79) Uwuigbe, U., & Jimoh, J. (2012). Corporate environmental disclosures in the Nigerian manufacturing industry: A study of selected firms. *African Journal of Business Management*, 6(22), 6690–6697.
- 80) Uwuigbe, U., & Olayinka, M. U. (2011). Corporate social responsibility disclosures in Nigeria: A study of listed financial and non-financial firms. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 13(5), 159–172.
- 81) Wahyuningrum, I.F.S., Budihardjo, M.A, Muhammad, F.I, Djajadikerta, H.G. &Trireksani, T. (2020). Do environmental and financial performances affect environmental disclosures? Evidence from listed companies in Indonesia. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability* 8(2), 1047-1061. [http://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2020.8.2\(63\)](http://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2020.8.2(63))
- 82) Wu, H., & Li, J. (2023). The relationship between environmental disclosure and financial performance: mediating effect of economic development and information penetration. *Economic research-Ekonomiska istraživanja*, 36(1), 116-142. www.wbiconpro.com/110-Gupta.pdf.
- 83) Yahaya, K. H, Bamigbade, D & Ajiboye, .G (2023) The Effect of Corporate Governance on Environmental Disclosure by Listed Nigerian Consumer Goods Firms, *Jurnal Administrasi Bisnis*, 11(1), 53-64
- 84) Zaid, A.A.M., Wang, M., TF Abuhijleh, S., Issa, A., WA Saleh, M., & Ali, F. (2020). Corporate governance practices and capital structure decisions: the moderating effect of gender diversity. *Corporate Governance: The International Journal of Business in Society*, 20(5), 939-964.
- 85) Zalata, A. M., Ntim, C. G., Alsohagy, M. H., & Malagila, J. (2022). Gender diversity and earnings management: The case of female directors with financial background. *Review of Quantitative Finance and Accounting*, 58(1), 101-136.<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11156-021-00991-4>.